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FORMING STUDENTS' CONSCIENTIOUS ATTITUDE TO TECHNICAL TRANSLATION CLASSES IN A GLOBALIZED WORLD

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This paper examines the process of managing technologies in the orientation of the university students' personality forming in technical translation classes from the position of a system-based approach in the globalization context. Observations show that technical fields students use the choice of language for translation not with the aim of broadening their general horizons and raising their educational level, but with the intention of acquiring specific knowledge and competencies necessary in the present and future. Due to globalization and integration students migrate abroad. The educational system faces the challenge of increasing its competitiveness. Technical translation teachers need to: set clear, well-prepared tasks for students; to reveal the scientific basis of pedagogical principles and recommended methodological provisions; apply optimal loads in tasks; give short explanations before doing new exercises; use live speech; take into account the commonality of goals; create subgroups, targeted samples depending on the characteristics of students. Autonomous and distance learning are associated with the formation of their willingness and habits to work independently and actively, the ability to consciously evaluate their linguacultural experience and the ability to correct it, make their own independent decisions and take responsibility for the results of technical translation. The implementation of this principle provides the students' mastery of various strategies for working with the language, which are based on interdisciplinary subjects of the curriculum. Fulfilment of individual, differentiated by the level of complexity and subject matter tasks develops the skills of autonomous work, the ability to work with reference literature, individually formulate and transmit the information received to others, develops thinking and creativity.

Keywords: technology, globalization, translation, systems, management, training, personality, level, professionalism, subjects.

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1. Introduction

The influence of globalization on all aspects of society in the modern world can be discussed since the beginning of the 21st century. It leads to the internationalization of both production and society as a whole in the conditions of a forming information space. "We understand globalization as a process of global, political and cultural integration. The main characteristics of which are the world division of labor, migration on a planetary scale of monetary, human and production resources"[1].

2. Literature review

Analysis of changes in the geopolitical map of the world shows that in this area there is a struggle for space and leadership. Europe, led by Germany, Russia, China, Japan, and the countries of the Muslim world aspire to the role of such leaders [2].

All this is accompanied by integration processes, during which such associations formed in the world as:

EU (European Union Germany, France, Italy, Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg, 1993);

CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States);

SCO (Shanghai Cooperation Organization, which includes China, Russia, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, 2001);

BRICS (Association of five major national economies of countries, such as Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa, 2010);

NAFTA (Association of North American Countries: Canada, Mexico, USA, 1994);

UN (Global International Organization, 1945);

NATO (Intergovernmental Organization Military-Political Union, 1949);

OPEC (Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries, 1960);

GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council of the Arab States, United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Oman, Bahrain, Kuwait, 1981);

OSCE (Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, 1973);

ASEAN (Association of Southeast Asian Nations, 1967).

The geopolitical map of the world is being transformed. There is a struggle for a geopolitical space and leadership in this process. In addition to political unions, it is necessary to note the existence of no less significant organizations:

European Travel Commission,
International Air Transport (Association - industry trade group for airlines, which regulates international air travel),

International Civil Aviation Organization,
International Olympic Committee,
International Organization for Standardization,
National Tourism Organization (organization a government uses to promote the country),

Tourist Information Center,
United Nations,
United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization,
Visitor Information Center,
World Tourism Organization (also UNWTO),
World Heritage Site [3].

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of this study is consideration of student learning technologies in the context of globalization in the classroom on technical translation.

To accomplish the aim, the following tasks have been set:

1) to develop technologies for the formation of students' professional abilities;

2) to operate a diagnostic apparatus to regulate the effectiveness of training [4].

4. Research methods

Currently, issues of new technologies are being widely developed to implement the formation of human needs for translation of technical and scientific literature from foreign languages into a pre-systemically designed educational process of teaching.

In the context of the development of globalization and integration processes, the most active part of students are migrating abroad, and the domestic education system faces the challenge of increasing its competitiveness.

In the world market of educational services in the context of informatization of society, the rapid aging of professional knowledge, continuous modernization of production, population migration, society needs specialists, capable of professional reorientation and lifelong learning throughout their lives, access to quality higher education for everyone. The issues of the quality of education are studied by modern scientists at different levels of methodology. At the philosophical level, "quality" seems to be a synthetic category, an object of systematic research.

And at the general scientific level, pedagogical concepts and theories of quality management of the entire education system are built, forecasts are made and appropriate strategies for the management of higher education quality are developed. With the transition to a specific level, the problem of managing the quality of education is specified in relation to a specific pedagogical task.

The accession of Ukraine to the Bologna process required the presentation of the quality of Ukrainian education from the standpoint of international ISO standards as an integral characteristic of education and its results, expressed through the measure of their compliance with the ideas, existing in society about how education should be organized, what goals should be pursued in the educational process and what results should be formed at its output [5].

A distinctive feature of the pedagogical system for the formation of knowledge in technical translation is that it follows from a deeply thought-out, creative and constructive work on the assessment and harmonization of many factors that determine the effectiveness of the processes of formation of high-quality translation. At the same time, one cannot rely on standard and stereotypical old solutions to technical translation problems, but they should be solved creatively, consciously, using new technologies.

Pedagogical technology develops classical didactics, and this development is expressed in the earlier formulated works by Latyshev, Komisarov, and later in modern developments by Alekseeva, Chernovaty, Ko-

runets' [6–11]. The same approach is observed by foreign authors of Biker M., Kaindl K., Neubert A. [12–14]. In these works, the principles were used: structural and substantial integrity of the translation technology, didactic focus of the translation process, significant completeness of the solution of the problem of translation, social and environmental protection, and finally, the intensity of all processes.

In modern globalization processes, there is a relationship with concepts, such as: socialization, development, education, technological progress. It is known from Wikipedia, that education is a special area of public life, in which the interests of all its subjects intersect, starting from the state and ending with each individual member of society. It is it that ensures the continuity and stability of social life, while creating the prerequisites for its changes and dynamic development.

The construction of modern education on the basis of democratic principles not only makes it possible to introduce it into the general development of world civilization, but also becomes its daily need. It is the key to the progress and spread of democracy, which is necessary for active citizens, who have the knowledge, skills and values of a democratic life and without which a democratic culture will not flourish.

5. Results of the research

Currently, the concept of "pedagogical technology" has become the subject of many psychological and pedagogical studies, which reveal the general principles of technology in the education system. Analyzing the specialized literature, one can note the differences in theoretical approaches to explaining the essence and content of the pedagogical translation technology. The technology for managing the formation of students' personality in technical translation classes is based on the following theoretical components:

1. Management technology is a pedagogical project of a teacher of technical translation, a system of professional functions and tasks that he/she solves, which means it is necessary: a detailed description of specific work tasks in engineering; determination of intermediate and final results of the translation; description of the management process for the formation of the student's personality as a translator in practical classes.

2. The technology defines a system of transitions from the orientation of the personality of students to translation classes to the professional activities of the teacher, which determines: the prediction of compensatory and correctional controls in connection with individual specific results and unexpected inclusion of extraneous influences in the pedagogical process; development of a diagnostic apparatus, capable of recording the state of the "teacher-student" system in order to regulate the effectiveness of communication between them and the coordination of actions of the student and the trainers, to provide for the flexibility of management technology, its adaptability, the ability to change direct and indirect effects on students depending on intermediate results, and training the individual to introspect in his/her activities.

3. Management technology orientates students to achieve non-instant results, which indicates the need for:

predicting the difficulties, encountered by students in the translation classes, "designing" the appropriate support in groups and individually; creating an emotional and psychological atmosphere of the learning process.

The result of training is a stable and appropriate change in the mental state of the learner, which finds expression in the achievement of a certain level of knowledge, skills, upbringing and development.

If the pedagogical process is considered as a kind of technology, then it should include actions to change and further determine the learning outcomes [15]. The most important tasks of designing pedagogical technologies are: setting diagnostic goals for training; planning in space and time of algorithms and the sequence of technological operations of the educational process; development of criteria for assessing the quality of training; management of cognitive activity through a comprehensive description of the state of the object and through adjustable parameters of practical tasks.

In accordance with the functional control scheme, the stages are distinguished: diagnostic, design, organizational, controlling, analytical, correctiv. Each stage consists of invariant types of teacher activity in the form of

training blocks. These are blocks: tasks, content, means of pedagogical communication, methodological support, control and correction. The allocation of control and correction units is due to their importance not only in the management cycle, but also their importance in the implementation of each technological stage.

Each of these blocks of designing pedagogical technology has its own logic and features. They are closely related to each other, mutually intertwined and complemented. There is an improvement of each of the blocks, and the whole design strategy of pedagogical technology acquires its internal unity.

6. Conclusion

1. For an effective approach to teaching, it is necessary to develop a technology for the formation of professional skills of students in the classroom for technical translation.

2. A guaranteed result in the classroom on technical translation can be achieved only when using the diagnostics of the stages of training. Diagnostics allows you to control the quality of training of specialists in the educational process.

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